

Proposed pilots for international stakeholders

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Acronyms

ACTRIS = Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research Infrastructure

ACTRIS IMP = ACTRIS Implementation project

Cal/Val = Calibration/Validation (Cal/Val)

CARS = ACTRIS topical Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing

CCRES = ACTRIS topical Centre for Cloud REmote Sensing

DC-ARES = Aerosol REmote Sensing unit at the ACTRIS Data Centre

DC-CLU = CLOUD remote sensing Unit at the ACTRIS Data Centre

EARLINET = European Aerosol Research Lidar NETWORK

EEA = European Environment Agency

ESA = European Space Agency

EUMETSAT = European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites

FRM = Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM)

SWD = Staff Working Day

TNA = Trans-National Access

WG = working group

1 Introduction

The limited use of the current trans-national access (TNA) programs by international stakeholders is a significant shortcoming for making use of the available services provided by the atmospheric research facilities for the validation of European Earth Observation missions and instruments (S3, S5Pp, ADM-Aeolus, EarthCARE, etc.), considering that current advancements in atmospheric composition measurements require access to independent, high-quality, global observations provided by research infrastructures like ACTRIS.

Several international stakeholders were identified at the proposal writing stage as being potential users of the ATMO-ACCESS pilots: European Space Agency (ESA), Copernicus, European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), and European Environment Agency (EEA). Collaboration between ACTRIS partners and these stakeholders were previously organized in the framework of various research and/or service provision projects, however not in a highly coordinated manner that would allow extended use of the infrastructure. The TNA programs open through ACTRIS, ACTRIS-2, EUROCHAMP 2020, and ACTRIS IMP projects were not accessed by such international organizations, partially because they were not familiar with the opportunities, and partially because of the TNA rules and processes which do not fit their specific needs. International stakeholders target complex projects, involving a multitude of platforms and services, and extending over a long period of time. Moreover, they cannot handle by themselves the coordination and the technicalities of such projects, meaning that the access providers should actively be involved, together with the stakeholder, in the co-design and the implementation of the projects, not only for facilitating the access but indeed for planning and performing the measurements, analyzing the data, and producing the results in a form that the stakeholder can make use of.

Acknowledging all this, the ATMO-ACCESS project is currently exploring various options for making the international stakeholder access to atmospheric RIs more attractive and efficient, e.g., by combining services and by jointly utilizing the observatories, exploratory platforms, and central laboratories. A pilot TNA process was established in order to test and facilitate international

stakeholder access to facilities involved in ATMO-ACCESS, ensuring that we make the best use of the available resources and that all interested parties have the opportunity to contribute to the validation of European Earth Observation missions and instruments.

2 Process

The process was handled in several steps, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the process for defining the pilot projects and implementation plans

Steps 1 and 2 were organized to explore and discuss the scientific and technical focus of the pilot. Steps 3 and 4 were dedicated to identifying the more specific interests of the international stakeholders and prioritizing project ideas through an independent review. Selected projects were defined in further detail during steps 5 and 6, and passed through another independent review in step 7. Step 8 involves implementation of the projects and will last for almost the entire duration of ATMO-ACCESS.

2.1 Initializing the pilot

2.1.1 Definition of the focus

Due to the limited resources available, it was obvious that we had to focus the pilot on a subject that is a) of significant interest to more than one stakeholder; b) ensures scientific excellence while maintaining a competitive process; c) feasible to be implemented at ATMO-ACCESS facilities, at least partially, during the lifetime of the ATMO-ACCESS project and; d) having a real potential to test the TNA program in a way to allow the identification of weaknesses and limitations which, at the end, will lead to recommendations for future optimization.

Discussions were organized with an extended group of experts who volunteered to analyze the current needs of ESA, EUMETSAT, Copernicus and EEA, as well as opportunities that this pilot can provide in order to have significant impact in the timeframe of ATMO-ACCESS. The group was formally established in March 2022, as a follow up of the “Stakeholder Workshop” organized on 27th October 2021 during ACTRIS Week 2021, and was open to the international stakeholders, public authorities and the private sector.

The working group (WG) established for this pilot was comprised of 19 persons and organized its plenary meeting on 19th May 2022. After analyzing the various suggestions of the members, it was decided to launch a call dedicated to the Calibration/Validation (Cal/Val) activities of satellite atmospheric missions. The main reasons for the decision were: a) three out of the four previously identified stakeholders have an interest in this topic; b) a significant part of the services offered by ATMO-ACCESS involves synergistic observations at near-surface and in the atmospheric column, being particularly relevant for satellite Cal/Val; c) there is a window of opportunity to contribute to the Cal/Val of EarthCARE (to be launched in Spring 2024), as well as to the Cal/Val of the operational

Sentinels (soon under the responsibility of EUMETSAT), which cannot be missed; d) Cal/Val of satellite atmospheric missions will continue to be a topic of great interest after the end of ATMO-ACCESS, and can be pursued by the research infrastructures through their access programs, building towards the long-term sustainability and impact. International stakeholders are, thus, a major user community for which the use of the research infrastructure services can be optimized and made more attractive in the future.

2.1.2 Call for proposals

[The call](#) was opened in July 2022 and targeted international stakeholders (space agencies and programs, etc.) interested in implementing complex activities requiring physical, remote, virtual, recurring, and multi-platform access to ATMO-ACCESS facilities.

Interested parties were invited to submit a concept note summarizing their proposal. The template created for this call is attached (Annex 1). The applicants were asked to commit to participation in the co-design of the full project (if selected for implementation), and also to provide feed-back after implementation to enable the ATMO-ACCESS project to capture specific suggestions and recommendations for the optimization of future TNA programs of this nature.

2.1.3 Concept Notes

Three proposals were submitted: two by EUMETSAT to support the long-term Cal/Val of aerosol and clouds operational satellite products, and one by ESA to support the Cal/Val of the EarthCARE mission.

The EUMETSAT-Aerosol project focuses on using remote and virtual access to the Data Centre for validation of the EUMETSAT and Copernicus (operated by EUMETSAT) aerosol missions and products. More specifically it serves the following missions: EPS: GOME2/AVHRR/IASI (PMAp product), Sentinel-3: SLSTR and OLCI, EPS-SG: 3MI and Hyper-instrument with 3MI/METimage/Sentinel-5/IASI-NG (MAP product), CO2M: MAP, MSG: SEVIRI, MTG: FCI. Main activities considered are: provision of access to gapless ground-based aerosol product, having the quality better and/or similar to satellite mission accuracy, and supported by documentation; tailoring of algorithms to meet specific needs; modification of measurement schedules to better match the times of satellite overpasses.

The EUMETSAT-Clouds project focuses on using remote and virtual access to the Data Centre for validation of cloud products from current and future satellite missions: The MSG/SEVIRI Optical Cloud Analysis (OCA) products currently disseminated by EUMETSAT, the future EPS-SG/METimage cloud mask (VII-02-CLD), OCA (VII-02-OCA), and cloud top pressure (CTP) products retrieved from the O2 A-band (VII-02-CTP), the future EPS-SG/3MI cloud products (3MI-02-CLD), MTG/FCI Cloud Mask and Scene Analysis products, the future MTG/FCI OCA products, the future Sentinel-3/OLCI and SLSTR cloud mask (S3-SYN-CM) and CTP products (S3-OLCI-CTP), the future cloud products from CO2M/CLIM and MAP. Main activities considered are: to secure product generation; to establish FRM dataset; to provide data access.

The ESA EarthCARE project focuses on using physical, remote and virtual access to aerosol and cloud remote sensing facilities in order to prepare and pursue specific activities for calibration and validation of EarthCARE data products. It involves fixed observation stations, central laboratories, access to the Data Centre and, based on opportunity, mobile platforms. Main activities considered are: preparation of the QA/QC and data preparation tools, as well as plans for validation; preparation for data acquisition and rapid processing; pre-launch network rehearsal campaign with fast data delivery; post-launch validation with Near Real Time data delivery; intercalibration with other networks and instruments contributing to Cal/Val.

2.1.4 First evaluation

The independent evaluation of the concept notes was entrusted to a specific evaluation panel established for this purpose. Panel members were identified among international specialists with broad expertise in remote sensing, satellite Cal/Val, and previous knowledge of the atmospheric RIs. Ten experts were then invited to participate in the pilot TNA assessment, with eight accepting the task. Reviewers performed the individual evaluation of concept notes remotely, considering the relevance and impact of the proposed activities, and the implementation feasibility under the TNA scheme in ATMO-ACCESS.

A review meeting took place on 10th November 2022, involving the panel experts, ATMO-ACCESS Coordination, Strategic TNA/VA Board, project office, and TNA management to consider the individual assessment outcomes and decide which proposals to progress to the second stage of the process. All the 3 concept notes were retained for the co-design phase, with final decisions on approval/rejection for implementation to be taken after a new review of the co-designed projects and selection meeting to assess the suitable facilities, the resources available and those required for the Pilot.

2.2 Co-design of the pilot projects

2.2.1 Establishment of the co-design Expert Group

In order to further develop the concept notes and establish the project implementation plans, an Expert Group was constituted. The Expert Group was further split in three working groups, one for each project, so that the co-design could be done in parallel. Members of the ATMO-ACCESS community (potential providers, TNA experts) were invited to submit a short CV and to fill in a matrix of expertise. Based on this information (background and expertise) they have been allocated to one or more working groups. Representatives of the stakeholders were invited to participate, according to their commitment in the concept notes. The Expert Group currently has 38 members, comprising 3 ESA representatives, 8 EUMETSAT representatives, 4 ATMO-ACCESS TNA experts, 4 representatives of the ARES and CLU Data Centre units, 4 representatives of the CARS and CCRES Topical Centres, and 15 Cal/Val experts from observational facilities. One Rapporteur (typically a member of the ATMO-ACCESS community) and a deputy (typically from the stakeholder) were selected for each of the working groups. Their responsibility was to organize technical meetings, to progress with the co-design of the specific pilot project, and to report to the Expert Group during plenary meetings.

The Expert Group organized six online plenary meetings between January and May 2023. Discussion topics evolved from clarifying the mission of the Expert Group to analyzing the TNA constraints applicable, quantifying the ATMO-ACCESS resources available for the pilot projects, deciding on the content of the project implementation plan, defining the objectives and the main activities of each pilot project, and establishing a process to select the providers. At each plenary meeting, the Rapporteurs from the three working groups gave an update on the progress of their co-designed pilots.

2.2.2 Call for providers

An official call for providers was launched on 15th March 2023. It was distributed via email to the aerosol and cloud remote sensing mailing lists (ATMO-ACCESS, ACTRIS, EARLINET, CLOUDNET), which include both ATMO-ACCESS providers and Principal Investigators outside ATMO-ACCESS. Potential providers received a summary of each pilot project, including the list of main activities and time schedule. They were asked to confirm their participation in one or more of the pilot projects, and to provide additional information about the site and the available instrumentation.

The number of applications received is presented in the table below.

Type of facility	Pilot project		
	EUMETSAT Aerosol	EUMETSAT Clouds	ESA EarthCARE
ATMO-ACCESS	5	4	25
Central Facility (Topical Centre)	2		2
Fixed observation platform	3	3	17
Mobile observation platform		1	6
Voluntary participation	12	6	23
Central Facility (Data Centre)	2	1	2
Central Facility (Topical Centre)	2	2	4
Fixed observation platform	7	2	16
Mobile observation platform	1	1	1
Total	17	10	48

In order to estimate the resources needed for the implementation of each pilot project, the Expert Group developed a simulator for the access units, which takes into consideration the average effort for an aerosol / cloud remote sensing facility to participate in the defined activities. Particular attention was given to translating the effort for each activity into access units that each provider would use. The three candidate pilot projects, the list of the potential providers and the estimated average effort for an aerosol / cloud remote sensing facility were presented and discussed at the ATMO-ACCESS General Meeting, 29th – 31st March 2023, Valencia. Feed-back from the community was taken into consideration for the pilot project implementation plans.

The Expert Group also analyzed the situation and clarified by direct interaction with the individual providers, some of the aspects related to the compliance of instrumentation and/or availability of the resources. This step was especially important to understand the quantity of work required from the Topical Centres and the Data Centre, which are supposed to ensure the QA/QC of the instruments and data products for all participating facilities.

Additional clarifications were provided by the Expert Group during the online meeting with the potential TNA providers (4th April 2023). This meeting was specifically important for defining the scale and the ambition of the pilot projects, compromising between the needs of the stakeholders on one hand, and the number of facilities which can be mobilized, on the other hand.

As a follow-up to this meeting, the potential providers were asked to refine the estimated number of access units required at their facility to implement the activities planned in the pilot projects, and to specify how the effort be financially covered. This exercise showed that the pilot (composed of the three pilot-projects) extends beyond the borders of the ATMO-ACCESS project, with many access providers willing to use internal (or national) resources in order to complement ATMO-ACCESS resources. Extending the list of providers beyond ATMO-ACCESS contributes to a better geographical coverage of the Cal/Val activities but also brings additional complexity to the management and the implementation of the pilots, e.g., some of the providers being less familiar with the TNA vocabulary and principles.

2.2.3 Elaboration of the pilot projects

At the last plenary meeting (3rd May 2023), the Expert Group finalized the list of providers in each pilot, as well as their estimated access units based on the input from the providers. The principle was to plan the pilot projects at the appropriate scale, so that: a) the objectives of each pilot project are met; b) the three pilot projects, together, do not consume more than 20% of the ATMO-ACCESS available access units; c) each ATMO-ACCESS provider has sufficient access units to participate in the pilot project activities as planned; c) most of the ATMO-ACCESS providers involved in the pilot have sufficient access units to be involved with other calls as well.

Based on the decisions made, the working groups have finalized the three pilot projects offline, and

submitted the implementation plans to the ATMO-ACCESS Coordination Office on 15th May 2023. Maps showing the participating fixed observation sites (mobile platforms and central facilities not shown here) are provided below.

Figure 2 Geographical distribution of the fixed observation sites contributing to the pilot projects for Cal/Val of satellite atmospheric missions: world (upper panels) and Europe (lower panels) maps; ATMO-ACCESS (right panels) and all (left panels) sites. ACTRIS-compliant aerosol remote sensing observations in green; ACTRIS-compliant cloud remote sensing observations in blue; ACTRIS-compliant aerosol and cloud remote sensing observations in red; other aerosol remote sensing and/or cloud remote sensing observations in grey

The maps above show the high level of interest from providers within and outside ATMO-ACCESS to participate in the pilots, as well as the wide and dense geographical distribution of the observation sites (extending globally), which ESA and EUMETSAT appreciate and are eager to take on board for the Cal/Val activities.

2.2.4 Second evaluation

The second evaluation of the projects resulting from the co-design phase was entrusted to the same experts who reviewed the concept notes, excluding those who had a role (as facility providers, consulted experts, etc.) in the co-design phase.

For the new assessment, experts were asked to fill in the review form originally used for the concept notes to enable comparison, appreciate the developments, and see if the co-designed projects adequately addressed comments and points raised at the time of the first evaluation. The results of the new individual evaluations were analyzed and discussed in a plenary session held on 12th June

2023, attended by the Reviewers, the WP6 Team and Task leaders, the Strategic TNA/VA Board, the project coordination, and the TNA Management Team.

The selection committee was highly impressed by the quality and potential impact of the proposed projects and, after considering carefully all the resources available, decided to allow all three pilot projects to progress to the implementation phase.

3 Summary of the pilot projects

3.1 Pilot project 1: EUMETSAT-Aerosol

The goal of this pilot project is to secure reliable access to accurate fiducial reference measurements (FRM) from the ACTRIS ground-based stations for the validation and long-term monitoring of all EUMETSAT aerosol products, through the entire lifetime of the current EUMETSAT aerosol missions (i.e., until 2045 at least).

Main activities:

- Provision of additional aerosol parameters (e.g. aerosol layer heights) and parameters tailored for specific EUMETSAT instruments/needs
- Provision of ACTRIS products from all available ground-stations with a timeliness suitable to support the Cal/Val of EUMETSAT operational aerosol missions and easy access for the users.
- Provision of ACTRIS products from all available ground-stations with quality aligned to FRM standards and consistency among all available ground-stations.
- Reprocessing of historical data (e.g. lidar networks) to obtain ACTRIS products with the format and requirements implemented in the previous tasks.

Timeline: June 2023 – October 2024; to be continued in the framework of the ACTRIS access program

Providers: ACTRIS Data Centre unit responsible for aerosol remote sensing data products (DC-ARES), ACTRIS Topical Centre responsible for column aerosol remote sensing instrumentation (CARS-ASP-UVA)

Type of access: remote (development of tailored products) and virtual (provision of access to tailored data products)

Estimated number of access units: 82 SWD, out of which 82 SWD supported by ATMO-ACCESS

The full implementation plan of this pilot project is provided in Annex 2.

3.2 Pilot project 2: EUMETSAT-Clouds

The goal of this pilot project is to secure reliable access to accurate fiducial reference measurements (FRM) from the ACTRIS ground-based stations for the validation and long-term monitoring of all EUMETSAT cloud products, through the entire lifetime of the current EUMETSAT cloud missions (i.e., until 2045 at least).

Main activities:

- Provision of additional cloud parameters and (if possible) parameters tailored for specific EUMETSAT instruments (e.g. cloud fraction within the footprint of a given instrument, etc.);
- Provision of ACTRIS-Cloudnet products from all available ground-stations with a timeliness suitable to support the Cal/Val of EUMETSAT operational cloud missions and easy access for the users;
- Provision of ACTRIS-Cloudnet products from all available ground-stations with quality aligned to FRM standards and consistency among all available ground-stations
- Reprocessing of historical data from the Cloudnet network to obtain ACTRIS-Cloudnet products with the format and requirements implemented in the previous tasks.

Timeline: June 2023 – October 2024; to be continued in the framework of the ACTRIS access program

Providers: ACTRIS Data Centre unit responsible for cloud remote sensing data products (DC-CLU)

Type of access: virtual (provision of access to tailored data products)

Estimated number of access units: 40 SWD, out of which 40 SWD supported by ATMO-ACCESS.

The full implementation plan of this pilot project is provided in Annex 3.

3.3 Pilot project 3: ESA EarthCARE Cal-Val

The goal of this pilot project is to organize fast delivery of correlative datasets from a ground-based network for validation of the aerosol and cloud data products of EarthCARE, including preparation, coordination, development and implementation of common tools, production of harmonized metadata, development of tailored ACTRIS products, and thorough quality monitoring and intercalibration.

Main activities:

- Preparation for the tools and plans for validation
- Preparation for data acquisition and rapid processing
- Pre-launch network rehearsal campaign with fast data delivery
- Post-launch validation with Near Real Time (NRT) data delivery during commissioning phase
- Intercalibration with other networks and ESA's reference instruments

Timeline: June 2023 – October 2024

Providers: ACTRIS Data Centre units responsible for aerosol and cloud remote sensing data products (DC-ARES, DC-CLU), ACTRIS Topical Centres responsible for aerosol and cloud remote sensing instrumentation (CARS, CCRES), aerosol remote sensing and cloud remote sensing fixed observation stations (34) and mobile platforms (7).

Type of access: physical (direct comparison with reference systems, hands-on training), remote (development of tailored products, QA/QC of the instruments and data products, performance of observations according to simulated and real overpasses, validation of EarthCARE data products against ground-based data) and virtual (provision of access to tailored data products)

Estimated number of access units: 3030 SWD, out of which 1696 SWD supported by ATMO-ACCESS.

The full implementation plan of this pilot project is provided in Annex 4.

4 Conclusions

The pilot for international stakeholders raised the interest of ESA and EUMETSAT, two of the most important European stakeholders in the environmental domain. Following an extensive process involving experts from both ATMO-ACCESS and the stakeholders, three projects were designed, evaluated and selected for implementation. All have a significant level of complexity, either due to the very demanding needs of the stakeholder in terms of accuracy and timeliness, or due to the large variety of platforms and instrumentation required.

The co-design of the projects proved to be an important step in defining the details of the implementation plans. Although coordinated by the Expert Group, this work would have not been possible without the extensive interactions between the stakeholders and the providers. A significant number of meetings were necessary to find consensus on the scope of the pilot projects and decide on the best way to move forward. The stakeholders and some of the providers are still not sufficiently familiar with the vocabulary, rules and constraints of the TNA programs, which made the process slow.

Although the projects are competing for the same resources, when responding to the needs of stakeholders such as ESA and EUMETSAT, the competitiveness aspect is more like embedded into the

co-design of the projects rather than in the selection of the projects, as we will explain later.. In this task, we followed almost the same process as for a typical TNA, with formal templates, official submissions, independent evaluation of the concept notes and of the implementation plans. However, the scores obtained by each proposal in each of the steps were very close, meaning that it was impossible for the evaluation panels to choose between the projects. This is somewhat logical because stakeholders like ESA and EUMETSAT have specific and crucial roles in Europe. They have tremendous expertise, they know very well what they need and for what reason, and they are highly motivated to make use of research infrastructures like ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS in their Cal/Val programs because the research infrastructures are more strongly coordinated than partnerships and networks. The level of coordination impacts on the effectiveness of the implementation (less resources needed from the stakeholder to monitor and to guide the implementation) but also on the technical quality of the results (standard procedures, centralized processing, and a complete chain for quality assurance and quality control are necessary for achieving harmonized data sets for Cal/Val). The expressed needs of such stakeholders in the TNA projects were perfectly documented and justified, making the prioritization very difficult.

While progressing with the co-design, the Expert Group realized that although the three projects are competing for resources, in all other aspects they are complementing each other. Moreover, the way that these pilot projects have been designed and are to be implemented is a first-ever activity which could serve as a template for the future long-term services that could be offered to ESA (research satellites) and EUMETSAT (operational satellites), promising a high impact. Having these stakeholders as users is important not only for the sustainability of the research infrastructures and for science, but also, indirectly, for society. The design of each project was done to fit into the available resources, which unavoidable led to a smart selection of activities to be implemented, as well as of the facilities providing access. The competition for resources was therefore organized under the coordination of the Expert Group and had as main scope to maximize the scientific impact of each project within the limits of the budget. In other words, the focus during the co-design was shifted from “writing the best implementation plan so that this project is selected for implementation in ATMO-ACCESS”, to “how to make the best use of the available but limited resources so that all three projects can be implemented in ATMO-ACCESS”. The three working groups were not competing but collaborating to make this possible. The presence of representatives from ATMO-ACCESS and the stakeholders in the plenary meetings of the Expert Group was crucial for highlighting concerns, sharing experiences and finding solutions.

As a conclusion, we recommend excluding the competition between TNA projects promoted by international stakeholders as the current process is not very efficient for involving such important stakeholders for which the TNA instruments is too complex to adapt to. In the case of this pilot, we estimate a delay of around 6 months. Moreover, our experience showed that, with each meeting and with each new document or bureaucratic request, the interest of the stakeholders decreased. We believe that there is no need to validate the access request made by a well-known international stakeholder. Instead, the focus should be on the co-design which should guarantee the best use of resources for a maximum impact. We found that the role of the Expert Group is crucial in efficiently planning the activities and timeline, selecting the access providers, and quantifying the resources to be mobilized. With a balanced composition of the Expert Group and a clear mandate, the entire process can be confined in several meetings and several weeks of offline work.

5 Further work

The pilot projects now enter into the implementation phase. All providers will be asked to sign a commitment letter. For each pilot project a Management Board (MB) will be constituted. The role of the MB is to coordinate the implementation of the project as planned, and to report on the achievements.

Templates for regular reporting will be developed. Regular reporting on access provision is foreseen

to replace the usual “Confirmation of Access”. These reports shall be issued by the provider, accepted by the pilot project MB and approved by the ATMO-ACCESS Coordination Office. The possibility to implement the reporting process as an online workflow will be investigated.

Feedback and recommendations for optimizing the TNA program will be collected closer to the end of the implementation phase from all actors involved: the stakeholders, the providers and the ATMO-ACCESS Coordination Office.

A summary of the reports, feedback and recommendations will be embedded into *D6.5 Report on evaluation of the TNA pilots and future recommendations* (month 44).

References

[ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 2.1 Report on the current user needs as related to the historically offered access ways](#)

[ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 6.1 General Design Concept for flexible access modalities](#)

ANNEX 1: Template of the concept note

Logo of the stakeholder

Concept note (template)

International stakeholder

Name:

Address (headquarter):

Short description of the mission of the stakeholder and its main responsibilities

(max. 5 lines)

Contact person

Name:

Position:

Contact (email, phone):

Project proposal

1. Atmospheric satellite mission concerned

(title, acronym, relevant website)

2. Scientific relevance of the satellite mission in the ATMO-ACCESS field

(max. 1/2 page)

What are the instruments operated by the mission and the main data products?

How is the scientific community and the society benefiting from this satellite mission?

Why is ATMO-ACCESS relevant for the Cal/Val of this satellite mission?

3. Description of the need for TNA

(max.1/2 page)

Who are the actors involved (users/contractors, final beneficiaries, target groups, etc.)?

What are the problems to be resolved and the needs to be met?

What are the types of ATMO-ACCESS facilities whose services are needed?

4. Foreseen time schedule

Start date (*month, year*):

Estimated end date (*month, year*):

5. Main actions to be pursued under the TNA scheme

5.1 Action title 1

(max. 5 lines)

5.2 Action title 2

(max. 5 lines)

5.n. Action title n

(max. 5 lines)

Logo of the stakeholder

6. Expected impact in case the project is implemented

(max. 1/2 page)

What are the main expected results of the project?

Who will benefit from the results of the project (directly and indirectly)?

By this we commit to actively participate in the co-design of the TNA project and to provide feed-back to ATMO-ACCESS during and after the implementation.

Name & signature

Date

ANNEX 2: Implementation plan for the EUMETSAT-Aerosol pilot project

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Pilot project implementation plan ACTRIS products for the validation of EUMETSAT Aerosol Products

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Date: 2023-05-15

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1 Goals

The ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) high quality data and infrastructure services offer a crucial source of ground-based reference data for the validation of remote sensing L2 Aerosol products generated at EUMETSAT (European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites). EUMETSAT is currently setting the requirements, plans, tools and reference data for the overall EPS-SG and MTG Cal/Val facilities. Moreover, EUMETSAT already retrieves and disseminates aerosol products from the Metop Polar Multi-Sensor Aerosol product (PMAp) and Copernicus Sentinel-3 mission and will extend this service to the future aerosol mission and products.

In this context, the goal of this pilot project is to secure reliable access to accurate fiducial reference measurements (FRM) from the ACTRIS ground-based stations for the validation and long-term monitoring of all EUMETSAT aerosol products, through the entire lifetime of the current EUMETSAT aerosol missions (i.e., until the mid-40es at least).

The complexity of this purpose (i.e. serving/meeting multi-mission requirements, providing long-lasting and reliable access, etc.) requires a dedicated development and tuning of the requested FRMs, specific for aerosol missions and divergent from FRMs developed for other purposes (e.g. validation of aerosols, etc.)

The specific objectives of the Cal/Val for the EUMETSAT L2 Aerosol products are listed below, and they require FRM standards, following the guidelines outlined by the GEO/CEOS Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO, see <https://qa4eo.org>):

- Gapless ground-based aerosol product quality better and/or similar to satellite mission accuracy:
 - Measurements traceable to standard and/or community recognized best practices / standard operating procedures
 - Consistent and traceable processing
 - Long-term data availability in order to cover mission lifetimes.
 - Timeliness of ideally less than 48h (for satellite/product performance monitoring purposes).
- Data access & format of the ground-based aerosol products:
 - Easy access to data, central facility when dealing with networks
 - Widely used NetCDF format is preferred

- Documentation:
 - Product lists that can be supported/provided
 - Detailed products descriptions, including description of measurements, retrievals/processing, uncertainties, limitations, etc.
 - Description of data access & policy for use
- Test updated algorithms, configurations files, new/updated auxiliary data sets, etc., before their introduction in the operational environment.
- Tailoring of algorithms to meet specific needs, modification of measurement schedules to better match satellite overpasses time.

2 Implementation

2.1 Tasks

The tasks of this pilot project aim at the implementation of these improvements, which covers the following generic topics:

- Task 1: Provision of additional aerosol parameters (e.g. aerosol layer heights) and parameters tailored for specific EUMETSAT instruments/needs e.g.:
 - Modification of measurement schedules to better match satellite overpasses time;
 - Area measurements of aerosols covering the footprint of a given instrument;
- Task 2: Provision of ACTRIS products from all available ground-stations with a timeliness suitable to support the Cal/Val of EUMETSAT operational aerosol missions and easy access for the users. The associated cloud detection should also be provided in order to select cloud free scenes or assess the cloud contamination level in case of aerosol-cloud mix (relevant for microphysics);
- Task 3: Provision of ACTRIS products from all available ground-stations with i) quality aligned to FRM standards and ii) consistency among all available ground-stations in terms of:
 - Product content & format;
 - Consistent and traceable processing;
 - Documentation , including description of measurements, retrievals/processing, uncertainties, limitations, etc.;
 - Product quality and standards;
 - Policy for use.
- Task 4: Reprocessing of historical data (e.g lidar networks) to obtain ACTRIS products with the format/requirements implemented in the previous tasks. This

task will provide a suitable reference dataset for the validation of climate data record from PMAp aerosol products.

2.2 Aerosol Products

Table 1: Aerosol Product list based on EPS-SG Aerosol Requirements

Parameter	Horizontal resolution	Mission	Vertical resolution	Accuracy
Cloud detection	Pixel@4km Pixel@500m	3MI VII	N/A	5%
Aerosol Optical Depth	Clear pixel	3MI	N/A	0.05
Aerosol Type	Clear pixel	3MI	N/A	4 classes
Aerosol Layer height	Clear pixel	3MI/UVNS	N/A	1km
Aerosol Effective Radius	Clear pixel	3MI	N/A	0.6 μm
Aerosol single scattering albedo	Clear pixel	3MI	N/A	0.2
Aerosol refractive index	Clear pixel	3MI	N/A	N/A
Volcanic ash	Clear pixel	VII	N/A	detection
UV Aerosol index	Clear pixel	UVNS	N/A	0.1

EUMETSAT is assessing the FRM needs per product as identified in the Cal/Val plans and mission End User Requirements (EURD) which are based on user surveys and approved by the EUMETSAT Member States. The EPS-SG requirements are given as example in Table 1 as their wide range of aerosol parameters cover the current and future needs for the EUMETSAT aerosol missions including the needs for the COPERNICUS missions.

2.3 Timeline

The expected schedule of the development proposed in this pilot project is illustrated in Figure 1 and is as follows:

- This development plan will be submitted for evaluation by April 2023;
- The ATMO-ACCESS project will finish by April 2025. Thus the activities proposed under this TNA have to be developed over the next ~2 years and completed by April 2025;
- The long term monitoring of the quality, timeliness, etc., of ACTRIS aerosol profiling products extends beyond the ATMO-ACCESS project. This point is essential for the use of the products in the EUMETSAT Cal/Val and monitoring facility up to the 2040s. Thus, this task will fall under the responsibility of the data provider.

Figure 1: Gantt chart of the development proposed in this pilot project.

2.4 Participants & responsibilities

EUMETSAT presents its implementation plan in the role of stakeholder and user (this last specified in Sect. 3). As stakeholder, EUMETSAT commits to provide the following inputs and support of the proposed developments:

- This implementation plan;
- Testing of the ACTRIS aerosols profile products (e.g., testing of data access & download, format/content check, etc.) at any stage of the development, with complete report in the form of technical note. The EUMETSAT team involved in this testing is the one presenting this TNA, specifically:
 - Thierry Marbach (reference person for questions and reporting, technical support);
 - Carlos Toledano (Rapporteur of this pilot project);
 - Bertrand Fougne, Julien Chimot, Margarita Vazquez Navarro, Pepe Phillips (aerosol Cal/Val experts/advisors);
 - Henda Guerhazi, Andriy Holdak, Soheila Jafariserajehlou, Edouard Martins, Sruthy Sasi (technical support).
 - Although the data requested by EUMETSAT in this TNA will likely be used by other users around the world (see section 3), EUMETSAT does NOT take any responsibility or commits in any activity involving them (i.e. it does not lead or coordinate requests of other users, etc.).

Finally yet importantly, EUMETSAT expects ATMO-ACCESS to take on the role of leader and coordinator of the proposed development, i.e.:

- Design how ACTRIS will set up this pilot project;
- Interface between users and provider (i.e. ACTRIS teams);
- Define responsibility for specific user requests within ACTRIS and other teams;
- Harmonize the procedures used within the ACTRIS infrastructures.

2.5 Resources

This pilot project requires the use of the following facilities and resources:

- Processing facilities;
- Storage facilities;
- Test and evaluation of new products (with EUMETSAT support, see section 2.4);
- Easy data access (both virtual access, i.e. VA, and physical/remote access, i.e. TNA) and download protocol;
- Documentation (how to add the standards to other sites/networks);
- Resources in terms of “person” effort, units and budget.

Two types of access are planned in this project. On the one hand, Remote Access will be used for the necessary developments at the Data Center and the Topical Center, for data selection, formatting and implementation of the working flow for both photometer and lidar aerosol data. This effort is estimated in 20 SWD. On the other hand, Virtual Access is planned for the continuous access to aerosol data products as well as the reprocessing of historical data, with a total effort of 62 SWD distributed between Data Center and Topical Center units, as shown in the following table. These access units (82 SWD in total) will be funded by ATMO-ACCESS project and carried out by DC-ARES and CARS-ASP-UVa units.

2.6 Summary table

Objective	Task	Start month	End month	Deliverable(s)	Provider(s)*	Type of access	Estimated no. of access units (SWD)
Implementation of the access to aerosol products	Data product selection, formatting and working flow according to EUMETSAT needs from ground-based photometers (Remote access) as described in tasks 1 to 4.	Jun. 2023	Oct. 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product user guide describing the new product content, format. etc. Documentation describing the workflow and the retrieval used for added parameters 	CARS-ASP-UVA	Remote	10
	Data product selection, formatting and working flow according to EUMETSAT needs from ground-based lidars. (Remote access) as described in tasks 1 to 4	Jun. 2023	Oct. 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update product user guide describing the new product content, format. etc. Documentation describing the workflow and the retrieval used for added parameters 	DC-ARES	Remote	10
Continuous access to aerosol data products (as soon as data are available)	Data provision (less than 48h after acquisition) for satellite/product performance monitoring purposes from photometers. (Virtual access) as described in tasks 1 to 4	Nov. 2023	Sep. 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to ACTRIS photometer data 	CARS-ASP-UVA	Virtual	21
	Data provision (less than 48h after acquisition) for satellite/product performance monitoring	Nov. 2023	Sep. 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to ACTRIS lidar data 	DC-ARES	Virtual	21

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Reprocessing of historical data (e.g. lidar networks) to obtain ACTRIS products with the format/requirements implemented in the previous tasks (climate data record)	Nov. 2023	Sep. 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Access to reprocessed historical data• Documentation describing the historical dataset (time coverage, available sites, etc.)	DC-ARES	Virtual	20
Total estimated access units (SWD)						82
Total estimated access units supported by ATMO-ACCESS (SWD)						82

3 Dissemination & exploitation plan

EUMETSAT presents this pilot project in the role of both stakeholder and main user (relative responsibilities described in section 2.4). As such, EUMETSAT commits to exploit as much as possible the results of this project and has identified the following points to maximize the dissemination and exploitation of the requested ACTRIS aerosol products at EUMETSAT and, more in general, in the “aerosol” user community:

- EUMETSAT commits to present Cal/Val results based on these products at conferences, workshops, in peer-reviewed papers, etc. The use of ACTRIS aerosol products coming from this ATMO-ACCESS pilot project will be acknowledged in any of these publications.
- The reports of the continuous monitoring of EUMETSAT products based on ACTRIS aerosol products will be publicly available to the users via dedicated pages (e.g., METIS, see <https://metis.eumetsat.int>);
- EUMETSAT will use ACTRIS aerosol products for the monitoring of its satellite aerosol products up to the mid-2040s (i.e., up to the end of life of the new generation satellites MTG and EPS-SG);
- EUMETSAT expects that the data provider will make the ACTRIS aerosol products of this project (and the related documentation) available to all users, both European and international;
- EUMETSAT expects that the data provider will advertise the ACTRIS aerosol products of this project via their webpage, providing links to download products, the relative documentation and, possibly, to peer-reviewed papers describing their retrieval.

EUMETSAT is engaged in many activities with the user community of aerosol products and has identified the following institutions/teams that may be potentially interested in using the ACTRIS-aerosol products requested in this pilot project:

- The EUMETSAT Scientific Service for Fiducial Reference Measurements for Copernicus Aerosol Product Cal/Val Activities;
- National research institutions and private companies spread over Europe working in the space sector and developing retrieval of remote sensing products (to mention a few: University of Lille, Universidad de Valladolid, GRASP-SAS, Météo France, etc.);
- International space agencies and institutions such as ESA, NASA, etc., which generate and disseminate their own aerosol products (i.e. for different purposes and/or using different algorithms, or from their own polar satellites) and may benefit from the use of ACTRIS aerosol products for validation purposes over Europe.

- National and International Meteorological agencies (such as ECMWF/CAMS) which assimilate EUMETSAT aerosol products.

Note that, as already mentioned in section 2.4, although the data requested by EUMETSAT in this TNA will likely be used by other users around the world, EUMETSAT does NOT take any responsibility or commits in any activity involving them (i.e., it does not lead or coordinate requests of other users, etc.).

4 Expected impact

In this section, we demonstrate the advantage of having the ACTRIS aerosol products at the level of FRM and the important role that this pilot project would play in establishing/improving the quality of space-based aerosol products at least for the next 2 decades.

Advantages of FRM measurements for wider impacts/applications:

- 1) The required tailored aerosol products per instrument would facilitate the use of the ACTRIS aerosol products for users who would not have approached the data;
- 2) The requested timeliness allows a widespread use of automated monitoring processing;
- 3) The consistency/traceability as FRM allows a standardized approach to validation using these in-situ products.

Role in establishing/improving the quality of space-based aerosol products (which benefits not only EUMETSAT but also the international community working on/with aerosol and atmospheric products more in general):

- 1) The first and most obvious impact of this dataset is the role it will play to tune the quality of EUMETSAT aerosol products over Europe. Active space and ground-based instruments (lidars and photometers) have established themselves as a trustworthy source for aerosol detection validation during the last years.
- 2) The same reasoning as above applies to aerosol products generated and disseminated by other institutions (ESA, NASA, and NOAA) and /or using other polar satellites which like EUMETSAT, will have to rely on ground-based ACTRIS measurements for validation over Europe, given the lacking/uncertain availability of active space-based measurements after ~2030.

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- 3) The quality of aerosol products has a domino effect on the quality of several other coproducts like trace gases (especially greenhouse gases), surface and marine products etc.), because all these retrievals rely on auxiliary aerosol information for air quality, height assignment of atmospheric features, etc.
- 4) The established FRM dataset can be used not only as reference for the monitoring and validation of current satellite aerosol products, but also as reference for the design and development of future cloud missions (e.g., assessment of the impact of new channels on the retrieved aerosol parameters, impact of new algorithms or algorithm updates, etc.).

Annex 1: List of acronyms

3MI	Multi-Viewing Multi-Channel Multi-Polarisation Imaging
ACTRIS	Aerosols, clouds and trace gases research infrastructure
AE	Angstrom exponent
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
ARES	Aerosol Remote Sensing Database (part of ACTRIS data center)
ASP	Automatic Sun Photometer
ATMO-ACCESS	Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities (this project)
Cal-Val	Calibration-validation
CAMS	Copernicus Atmospheric Measurement System
CARS	Center for Aerosol Remote Sensing (Topical Center of ACTRIS)
CO2M	Copernicus CO2 Monitoring Mission
DC-ARES	Data Center, Aerosol Remote Sensing unit (part of ACTRIS)
EPS	EUMETSAT Polar System
EPS-SG	EPS Second Generation
ESA	European Space Agency
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EURD	End User Requirements
EURD	End User Requirement Documents
FCI	Flexible Combined Imager onboard MTG

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FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurement
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GRASP	Generalized Retrieval of Atmosphere and Surface Properties
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MAP	Multi Angle Polarimeter onboard CO2M
METIS	Monitoring & Evaluation of Thematic Information from Space
MSG	Meteosat Second Generation
MTG	Meteosat Third Generation
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRT	Near Real Time
OLCI	Ocean & Land Colour Instrument
PMaP	Metop Polar Multi-Sensor Aerosol product
QA4EO	Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation
QC	Quality control
S3	Sentinel 3
SEVIRI	Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) onboard MSG
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SWD	Staff Working Days

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TNA	Trans-National Access
UVa	University of Valladolid
UVNS	Ultraviolet Visible Near-infrared Shortwave (UVNS) spectrometer onboard Sentinel 5
VA	Virtual Access
VII	EPS-SG Visible Infrared Imager

ANNEX 3: Implementation plan for the EUMETSAT-Clouds pilot project

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Pilot project implementation plan ACTRIS-Cloudnet products for the validation of EUMETSAT cloud products

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1 Goals

1.1 Current situation

The ACTRIS high quality data and infrastructure services offer a crucial source of ground-based reference data for the validation of remote sensing L2 cloud products generated at EUMETSAT. EUMETSAT is currently setting the requirements, plans, tools and reference data for the overall EPS-SG and MTG Cal/Val facilities. Moreover, EUMETSAT already retrieves and disseminates cloud products from the Copernicus Sentinel-3 mission and will extend this service to the future Sentinel-4 and Sentinel-5 (part of the EPS-SG and MTG payload, respectively).

In this context, the goal of this pilot project is to secure reliable access to accurate fiducial reference measurements (FRM) from the ACTRIS ground-based stations for the validation and long-term monitoring of all EUMETSAT cloud products, through the entire lifetime of the current EUMETSAT cloud missions (i.e., until the mid-40es at least).

The complexity of this purpose (i.e. serving/meeting multi-mission requirements, providing long-lasting and reliable access, etc.) requires a dedicated development and tuning of the requested FRMs, specific for cloud missions and divergent from FRMs developed for other purposes (e.g. validation of aerosols, etc.)

The specific objectives of the Cal/Val for the EUMETSAT L2 Cloud products are listed below, and they require FRM standards, following the guidelines outlined by the GEO/CEOS Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO, see <https://qa4eo.org>):

- To establish and monitor the quality of L2 products using independent means, i.e., data from other satellites or ground-based based observations. Determination of the product quality is intended in terms of precision, accuracy, stability, and continuity/consistency in line with established principles for the generation of climate data records. Wherever possible, product quality is expressed in terms of error characteristics, and traced to common standards.
- To achieve state-of-the-art performance from the L2 algorithms and generate products that meet or exceed as much as possible the user requirements.
- To maintain the quality of L2 products within the user requirements by coping with the impact of the degradation of the instruments performance due to aging and/or any changes on the processing/quality of L1B radiance products over the entire mission lifetime.
- To test the performance of revised versions of L2 cloud algorithms;
- To test updated algorithms, configurations files, new/updated auxiliary data sets, etc., before their introduction in the operational environment. The need of such updates may arise from the outcome of the tasks mentioned above.

1.2 Specific objectives

EUMETSAT has explored the currently available ACTRIS-Cloudnet products generated and distributed by DC-CLU (see <https://cloudnet.fmi.fi>). Although they are suitable for a partial validation of EUMETSAT cloud products, several updates and refinements are needed in order to achieve FRM standards. The tasks of this pilot project (described in details in Sect. 2.1) aim at the implementation of these improvements, which covers the following generic topics:

- Task 1 (Sect. 2.1.1): Provision of additional cloud parameters and (if possible) parameters tailored for specific EUMETSAT instruments (e.g. cloud fraction within the footprint of a given instrument, etc.);
- Task 2 (Sect. 2.1.2): Provision of ACTRIS-Cloudnet products from all available ground-stations with a timeliness suitable to support the Cal/Val of EUMETSAT operational cloud missions and easy access for the users;
- Task 3 (Sect. 2.1.3): Provision of ACTRIS-Cloudnet products from all available ground-stations with i) quality aligned to FRM standards and ii) consistency among all available ground-stations in terms of:
 - o Product content & format;
 - o Consistent and traceable processing;
 - o Documentation;
 - o Product quality and standards.
- Task 4 (Sect. 2.1.4): Reprocessing of historical data from the Cloudnet network (some of the stations are going back to 2004) to obtain ACTRIS-Cloudnet products with the format/requirements implemented in the previous tasks. This task will provide a suitable reference dataset for the validation of climate data record from SEVIRI cloud products (OCA products).

2 Implementation

2.1 Tasks

The implementation of the tasks proposed in this pilot project starts from the existing ACTRIS-Cloudnet cloud profiling products generated/distributed by DC-CLU. Table 1 lists the parameters contained in these NetCDF products that are essential to validate the cloud parameters retrieved by EUMETSAT, and should be maintained in the requested updated NetCDF products.

Table 1: List of parameters available from the current ACTRIS-Cloudnet cloud profiling products generated/distributed by DC-CLU and used for the validation of EUMETSAT cloud products.

Parameter name	Product ID	Description & Comments
altitude	Classification	Altitude of site in meters
latitude	Classification	Latitude of site in degree_north

longitude	Classification	Longitude of site in degree_east
time	Classification	Time UTC of the observations (currently 2880 observation over 24h, i.e. time step 0.5min).
height	Classification	Height (in meters above mean sea level) of the probed atmospheric levels. This depends on the sensitivity of the cloud radar at the given site. Maximum height is currently ~11km in the Arctic and 15-18km in the tropics.
target_classification	Classification	Atmospheric target classifications at each time/height that can be distinguished by radar and lidar: 0: Clear sky 1: Cloud liquid droplets only 2: Drizzle or rain 3: Drizzle or rain coexisting with cloud liquid droplets 4: Ice particles 5: Ice coexisting with supercooled liquid droplets 6: Melting ice particles 7: Melting ice particles coexisting with cloud liquid droplets 8: Aerosol particles, no cloud or precipitation 9: Insects, no cloud or precipitation 10: Aerosol coexisting with insects, no cloud or precipitation
cloud_base_height_agl	Classification	Height (in meters) of cloud base above ground level at each time
cloud_base_height_amsl	Classification	Height (in meters) of cloud base above mean sea level at each time
cloud_top_height_agl	Classification	Height (in meters) of cloud top above ground level at each time
cloud_top_height_amsl	Classification	Height (in meters) of cloud top above mean sea level at each time
detection_status	Classification	Reliability of the radar and lidar data used to perform the classification at each time/height: 0: Clear sky 1: Lidar echo only 2: Radar echo but reflectivity may be unreliable as attenuation by rain, melting ice or liquid cloud has not been corrected 3: Good radar and lidar echoes 4: No radar echo but rain or liquid cloud beneath mean that attenuation that would be experienced is unknown 5: Good radar echo only 6: No radar echo but known attenuation 7: Radar echo corrected for liquid attenuation using microwave radiometer data 8: Radar ground clutter 9: Lidar clear-air molecular scattering
time	Model	Time UTC of the ECMWF forecast model used to infer cloud parameters (currently 25 models over 24h, i.e. time step 1h).

height	Model	Height above ground (in meters) of the ECMWF model levels (currently 137) at each ECMWF model time.
temperature	Model	Temperature (in K) of the ECMWF model at each time/height.
q	Model	Specific humidity (in kg/kg) of the ECMWF model at each time/height.
pressure	Model	Pressure (in Pa) of the ECMWF model at each time/height.
time	Liquid content	Time UTC of the observations (currently ~2550 observation over 24h, i.e. time step ~2min).
height	Liquid content	Height (in meters above mean sea level) of the probed atmospheric levels. This depends on the sensitivity of the instruments at the given site. Maximum height is currently ~11km in the Arctic and 15-18km in the tropics.
lwc	Liquid content	Liquid water content (in kg/m ³) at each time/height.
lwc_error	Liquid content	Error in liquid water content at each time/height (in dB).
lwp	Liquid content	Liquid water path (g/m ²) at each time.
lwp_error	Liquid content	Error in liquid water path (g/m ²).
iwc	Ice content	Ice water content (in kg/m ³) at each time/height.
iwc_error	Ice content	Error in ice water content at each time/height (in dB).
iwc_bias	Ice content	Possible bias in ice water content (in dB).

2.1.1 Task 1: Update of product's content

The first task of this pilot project is the update and inclusion of additional cloud parameters to the existing ACTRIS-Cloudnet cloud profiling products generated/distributed by DC-CLU, described in the previous section (Sect. 2.1). The requested updates shall be distinguished in:

- Additional “generic” cloud parameters, describe in Table 2.
- Parameters tailored for specific EUMETSAT instruments/needs (if possible), described in Table 3.

We are aware that the addition of the requested updates is trivial in some cases (e.g. “iwp” described in Table 2 would be just be a straightforward integration of “iwc” described in Table 1), while is challenging in others

For example, the quality of “reff” and “cot” estimates (Table 2) is scene-dependent; it is more challenging for liquid cloud, and not possible in case of precipitations at the surface. Thus, these parameters would not meet the requirement for robust retrievals across a wide variety of situations.

Another challenging example is the discrimination of dust and volcanic ash from other aerosol types (Table 2), which requires a polarimetric lidar currently available only at some ACTRIS sites. Thus, the retrieval of this parameter would not meet the requirement of homogeneous retrieval across the sites.

We stress that, for all these challenging retrievals, EUMETSAT is willing to accept/use estimates derived on a best-effort basis. It is understood that these (and possibly more) challenging parameters requested in Table 2 may be retrieved with strong caveats, limitations, etc., which will be taken into account within the EUMETSAT validation approach, as long as they are clearly documented following standard FRM prescriptions (see Task 3, Sect. 2.1.2).

Table 2: List of “generic” parameters to be added to the current ACTRIS-Cloudnet cloud profiling products.

Parameter name	Product ID	Description & Comments
target_classification	Classification	Modification of the existing target_classification parameter (described in Table 1) to distinguish dust and volcanic ash from other aerosol types.
cloud_base_height	Classification	Modification of the existing cloud_base_height_agl and cloud_base_height_amsl parameters (described in Table 1) to include the cloud base height for all detected cloud layers.
cloud_top_height	Classification	Modification of the existing cloud_top_height_agl and cloud_top_height_amsl parameters (described in Table 1) to include the cloud base height for all detected cloud layers.
cloud_base_height_error	Classification	Error in cloud base height at each time and for all detected cloud layers.
cloud_top_height_error	Classification	Error in cloud top height at each time and for all detected cloud layers.
reff	Classification	Cloud particle effective radius (in m) at each time/height.
reff_error	Classification	Error in cloud particle effective radius (in m) at each time/height.
cot	Classification	Cloud optical thickness at each time and for all detected cloud layers.
cot_error	Classification	Error in cloud optical thickness at each time and for all detected cloud layers.

iwp	Ice water content	Ice water path (g/m^2) at each time.
iwp_error	Ice water content	Error in ice water path (g/m^2).

Table 3: List of satellite-dependent parameters proposed for “tailored” ACTRIS-Cloudnet cloud products.

Parameter name	Product	Description & Comments
cfr	Tailored for FCI, VII, 3MI, IRS, IASI-NG, S3, CO2M, etc.	Cloud fraction within the footprint of the given instrument

2.1.2 Task 2: Ensure timeliness and easy data access

The EUMETSAT cloud products are subject to the strict scientific and operational requirements, among which the maintenance of products quality and stability globally and over the entire mission lifetime is the most challenging, because it requires a complex Cal/Val and monitoring facility. The facility shall be able to cope with the variety of cloud products generated at EUMETSAT, the diverse reference data (which may vary over time), the continuous effort to validate the products as homogeneously as possible across the globe and in different scenarios, the re-evaluation of quality after any algorithms and/or the processing facility change or updated of the, etc.

In this context, a significant issue is the flawed timeliness and availability of reference products (in this case the requested ACTRIS-Cloudnet profiling products), which may compromise EUMETSAT’s ability to use these products within the Cal/Val and monitoring facility.

Therefore, the scope of this task is to ensure the reliable timeliness and availability of the ACTRIS-Cloudnet profiling products requested in this pilot project. The timeliness of these products is a challenging point, because it depends not only on the data processing time but also on the time needed to transfer the collected data from the ground-station to the processing, which may not be synchronized across all sites.

Considering this challenge, we propose the following timeliness requirements:

- Timeliness < 48h from acquisition for data from all ACTRIS sites (a shorter timeliness within 3h would be ideal);
- Timeliness monitoring at the data processing center, in order to issues alarms to the users in case of delayed or non-available products;
- Daily update of the data repository;
- Availability of the repository > 99%;

- Easy user's access to the data repository. This includes not only access for internal EUMETSAT users, but also for other European and international users (if possible), as better explained in Sect. 3. We identified the following data access needs:
 - Virtual access to parameters that are already available (Table 1);
 - Remote access to parameters not already available (Table 2);
 - Access to parameters tailored for specific instruments, for which we require at least the implementation (Table 3).
- Readiness of the products with the above requirements (i.e. operational/routine phase) in the timeframe 2025 onward;
- Maintenance of the data generation and dissemination with the above requirements for the entire lifetime of the EUMETSAT current cloud missions (up to mid-2040s).

Of course, the technical implementation of the data access (e.g. NRT dissemination, or GTS flow, or active NRT push, of FTP repository, etc.) with the above requirements is a point of discussion between EUMETSAT and the data provider.

2.1.3 Task 3: Ensure quality and FRM standards

As already explained in Sect. 2.1, the quality and stability of reference data is a crucial point for the EUMETSAT Cal/Val and monitoring facility. Thus, the scope of the last task of this pilot project is to ensure that the requested ACTRIS-Cloudnet profiling products meet these requirements, i.e., comply with the standards of FRM (QA4EO, see <https://qa4eo.org>).

The product currently distributed by DC-CLU are very close to these requirements. Thus, the work proposed in this task aims at the refinements (and improvement, if needed) of what is already available, specifically in terms of:

- Ensure the quality and accuracy of the provided parameters and uncertainties (as per Table 1 to Table 3) via validation against space-based active lidar/radar measurements (e.g. using CALIPSO, CLOUDSAT, Aeolus, and EarthCARE overpasses to monitor/remove bias etc.) and inter-calibration with other networks and instruments contributing to Cal/Val (e.g. MPLNET, ADNet, LALINET, EMORAL, eVe, FRM4RADAR, etc.);
- Update (if needed) and maintenance of the current self-describing NetCDF format to make it fully compliant with the NetCDF CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Convention (<http://cfconventions.org/>) in terms of standard variable names, attributes, SI units, etc.
- Secure homogeneous product generation across all available ACTRIS sites, i.e. with consistent processing algorithms, content, quality and format of products;
- Ensure that the dataset is fully documented via a suitable product user guide including information on:
 - continuous update of the list of available sites;
 - description of the retrieval (homogeneous for all sites);

- description of uncertainties, caveats, limitations, etc. (may include site-specific issues, limitation etc.);
 - description of product's content and format;
 - description of data access and policy for use.
- Ensure that any change in the retrieval procedure, content and/or format of the product files, data access, etc., over time is clearly documented via update of the product user guide, and communicated to EUMETSAT and generic users (see Sect. 3) with due notice, to allow for adaptation of the EUMETSAT Cal/Val facility. The timescale for current EUMETSAT operational products is a 1-2 months notice for minor changes and updates, and a longer notice plus provision of test products for substantial changes.
 - **This pilot project** is focused on ACTRIS-Cloudnet profiling products obtained from the operational sites of the ACTRIS network, and **does NOT require any specific campaign**. However, EUMETSAT Cal/Val would benefit from analogous data from dedicated campaigns conducted in the context of other projects (e.g., using ACTRIS mobile units, or focused on limited periods, specific areas such as the Polar areas, etc.). Data from dedicated campaigns are already available from the DC-CLU portal. Thus, **the extension of the standards mentioned above to the cloud profiling products gathered during these possible campaigns is desirable.**

2.1.4 Task 4: Reprocessing of historical data

Together with operational near-real time cloud products, EUMETSAT generates and distributes cloud parameters for thematic climate data records (CDRs). The first version of Optimal Cloud Analysis (OCA) CDR from MSG/SEVIRI has been released in summer 2022 and covers the SEVIRI observation period from 2004 up to 2019, providing a homogenous cloud properties time series. It is generated at full MSG repeat cycle (15 minutes) frequency. Cloud properties retrieved by OCA are cloud top pressure, cloud optical thickness, and cloud effective radius, together with uncertainties (<https://www.eumetsat.int/release-oca-climate-data-record>).

The Cloudnet network of ground station is in operations since and the stations have collected data going back to 2004. Thus, these observations can provide a suitable reference dataset for the validation of SEVIRI OCA CDR (so far validate only against CloudSat/CALIPSO).

The work proposed in this task aims at generating this reference dataset and foresees the following:

- Reprocessing of historical data from the Cloudnet network to obtain ACTRIS-Cloudnet products with the format/requirements implemented in the previous tasks (i.e., to the level of FRMs);
- Access to the reprocessed dataset;
- Provision of the documentation describing this dataset (time coverage, available sites, etc.).

2.2 Timeline

The expected schedule of the development proposed in this pilot project is illustrated in Figure 1 and is as follows:

- This development plan will be submitted for evaluation by April 2023;
- The ATMO-ACCESS project will finish by April 2025. Thus the activities (Task 1, 2 and 3 as described in Sect. 2.1) proposed under this TNA have to be developed over the next ~2 years and completed by April 2025;
- The long term monitoring of the quality (e.g., validation against Cloudsat/Calipso and EarthCARE later on), timeliness, etc., of ACTRIS-Cloudnet profiling products extends beyond the ATMO-ACCESS project. This point is essential for the use of the products in the EUMETSAT Cal/Val and monitoring facility up to the mid-2040s. Thus, this task will fall under the responsibility of the data provider).

Figure 1: Gantt chart of the development proposed in this pilot project.

2.3 Participants & responsibilities

EUMETSAT presents his implementation plan in the role of stakeholder and user (this last specified in Sect. 3). As stakeholder, EUMETSAT commits to provide the following inputs and support of the proposed developments:

- This implementation plan;

- Testing of the ACTRI-Cloudnet profile products (e.g., testing of data access & download, format/content check, etc.) at any stage of the development, with complete report in the form of technical note. The EUMETSAT team involved in this testing is the one presenting this TNA, specifically the CLA CA (Clouds & Aerosols Competence Area) of the RSP (Remote Sensing & Products) division. This team includes:
 - o Reference persons for questions and reporting related to this project;
 - o Cloud and Cal/Val experts/advisors;
 - o Technical support.

- Although the data requested by EUMETSAT in this TNA will likely be used by other users around the world (see Sect. 3), **EUMETSAT does not take any responsibility** or commits in any activity involving them (i.e., it does not lead or coordinates request of other users, etc.).

DC-CLU is the current provider of the ACTRIS-Cloudnet products. Thus, EUMETSAT expects DC-CLU to have a direct involvement as “developer” of in the implementation proposed in this pilot project, specifically:

- Implementation, documentation, validation, testing, provision of products and deliveries, monitoring of the timeliness, etc. as described in Sect. 2.1;
- Advice/support on processing related issues;
- Advice/support on timeliness issues;
- Advice on aspects related to calibration and other aspects which do not rely on DC-CLU (i.e., rely on other groups within ACTRIS).

Finally yet importantly, EUMETSAT expects ATMO-ACCESS to take on the role of leader and coordinator of the proposed development, i.e.:

- Design how ACTRIS will set up this pilot project;
- Interface between users and provider (i.e. ACTRIS teams);
- Define responsibility for specific user requests within ACTRIS and other teams;
- Harmonize the procedures used within the ACTRIS infrastructures.

2.4 Resources

This pilot project requires the use of the following facilities and resources:

- Processing facilities (i.e., just 1 data center unit, DC-CLU);
- Storage facilities;
- Test and evaluation of new products (with EUMETSAT support, see Sect. 2.3);
- Easy data access (both virtual access, i.e. VA, and physical/remote access, i.e. TNA) and download protocol;
- Documentation (how to add the standards to other sites/networks);
- Resources in terms of “person” effort, units and budget.

2.5 Summary table

Objective	Task	Start month	End month	Deliverable(s)	Provider(s)	Type of access	Estimated no. of access units (SWD)
Update of product's content	1	May 2023	Oct 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to updated products Update product user guide describing the new product content, units. etc. Documentation describing the retrieval used for added parameters Multi-mission oriented framework to created tailored products 	DC-CLU	Virtual	14
Ensure timeliness and easy data access	2	Nov 2023	Feb 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation describing the timeliness and data access policy and guidelines. Access to data with new timelines 	DC-CLU	Virtual	10.5
Ensure quality and FRM standards	3	March 2024	July 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to updated products with FRM quality Update product user guide describing the updated content (e.g. addition of quality indicators, change in units, variable names, etc.) 	DC-CLU	Virtual	10.5
Reprocessing of historical data from the Cloudnet network	4	Aug 2024	Oct 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to reprocessed historical data Documentation describing the historical dataset (time coverage, available sites, etc.) 	DC-CLU	Virtual	5
Total estimated access units (SWD)							40
Total estimated access units supported by ATMO-ACCESS (SWD)							40

3 Dissemination & exploitation plan

EUMETSAT presents this pilot project in the role of both stakeholder (relative responsibilities described in Sect. 2.3) and main user. As such, EUMETSAT commits to exploit as much as possible the results of this project and has identified the following points to maximize the dissemination and exploitation of the requested ACTRI-Cloudnet products at EUMETSAT and, more in general, in the “cloud” user community:

- EUMETSAT commits to present Cal/Val results based on these products at conferences, workshops, in peer review papers, etc. The used of ACTRI-Cloudnet products coming from this ATMO-ACCESS pilot project will be clearly acknowledged in any of these publications.
- The reports of the continuous monitoring of EUMETSAT products based on ACTRI-Cloudnet products will be publicly available to the users via dedicated pages (e.g., METIS, see <https://metis.eumetsat.int>);
- EUMETSAT will use ACTRI-Cloudnet products for the monitor of its satellite cloud products up to the mid-2040s (i.e., up to the end of life of the new generation satellites MTG and EPS-SG);
- EUMETSAT expects that the data provider (i.e., DC-CLU in this case) will make the new ACTRI-Cloudnet products (and the related documentation) available to all users, both European and international;
- EUMETSAT expects that the data provider (i.e., DC-CLU in this case) will advertise the new ACTRI-Cloudnet products via their webpage, providing link to the product’s download, the relative documentation and, possibly, to peer review papers describing their retrieval.

EUMETSAT is engaged in many activities with the user community of cloud products (e.g., ICWG, user workshops, scientific collaborations, etc.) and has identified the following institutions/teams that may be potentially interested in using the ACTRI-Cloudnet products requested in this pilot project:

- The EUMETSAT Application Facilities (SAFs), especially the Nowcasting SAF (NWCSAF), the Climate Monitoring SAF (CM-SAF) and the Hydrology and water management SAF (H-SAF), which contribute to the development of cloud products from EUMETSAT satellites;
- National research institutions and private companies spread over Europe working in the space sector and developing retrieval of remote sensing products (to mention a few: University of Lille, SMHI, CNES, MeteoFrance, DLR, HYGEOS, Brockman Consult, Italian National Research Council, etc.);
- International agencies and institutions for meteorology (such as ESA, NOAA, CIMSS, NASA, JMA, CMA, etc.), which generate and disseminate their own cloud products (i.e. for different purposes and/or using different algorithms, or from their own polar satellites such as Suomi/VIIRS series, FengYun series, etc.), and may benefit from the use of ACTRI-Cloudnet products for validation purposes over Europe.

- National and International Meteorological agencies (such as ECMWF, UK MetOffice, DWD, NOAA etc.) which necessitate of in-situ observation for the validation of parametrizations of cloud microphysical properties in Numerical Weather Prediction models.

Note that, as already mentioned in Sect. 2.3, although the data requested by EUMETSAT in this TNA will likely be used by other users around the world, EUMETSAT does NOT take any responsibility or commits in any activity involving them (i.e., it does not lead or coordinates request of other users, etc.).

4 Expected impact

In this section, we demonstrate the advantage of having the ACTRIS-Cloudnet products at the level of FRM and the important role that this pilot project would play (if approved) in establishing/improving the quality of space-based cloud products at least for the next 2 decades.

Advantages of FRM measurements for wider impacts/applications:

- 1) The required tailored cloud products per instrument would facilitate the use of the ACTRIS-Cloudnet products for users who would not have approached the data;
- 2) The requested timeliness allows a widespread use of automated monitoring processing;
- 3) The consistency/traceability as FRM allows a standardized approach to validation using these in-situ products.

Role in establishing/improving the quality of space-based cloud products (which benefits not only EUMETSAT but also the international community working on/with “cloud” and atmospheric products more in general):

- 1) The first and most obvious impact of this dataset is the role it will play to tune the quality of EUMETSAT cloud products over Europe. Active space and ground-based instruments (radars and lidars) have established themselves as a trustworthy source for cloud detection validation during the last years and they are superior to any other validation data source when it comes to cloud products other than the cloud mask (especially COT/CTP). EUMETSAT cloud products from current operational satellites are successfully validated using CloudSat/CALIPSO. However, CloudSat/CALIPSO is reaching its end of life by the end of 2023. The obvious alternative is EarthCARE, which is still to be launched (currently expected for 2024) and had a designed lifetime of ~3 years. Thus, the availability of active space-based measurements for validation purposes after ~2030 is currently uncertain and jeopardizes the maintenance of the quality of EUMETSAT cloud products from new generation satellites (MTG, EPS-SG, Sentinel 3 etc.), which will last at least until mid-2040s. In this scenario, ground-based active instruments (and, hence, ACTRIS data) become crucial (i.e., the main and possibly only “active” reference measurements) for the validation of EUMETSAT cloud products.

- 2) The same reasoning as above applies to cloud products generated and disseminated by other institutions and /or using other polar satellites (NOAA, JMA, etc., as explained at the end of Sect. 3), which, as EUMETSAT, will have to rely on ground-based ACTRIS measurements for validation over Europe, given the lack/uncertain availability of space-based measurements after ~2030.
- 3) The quality of cloud products (especially the cloud mask) has a domino effect on the quality of several other atmospheric coproducts (aerosols, trace gases, temperature and humidity sounding, atmospheric motion vectors, surface and marine products etc.), because all these retrieval relies on auxiliary cloud information for cloud screening, height assignment of atmospheric features, etc. This, the quality of cloudy directly impact the quality of all these products;
- 4) The quality of cloud and other atmospheric products significantly affect many other meteorological applications, because several of them are ingested into forecast and climate models, used for nowcasting, etc.
- 5) The established FRM dataset can be used not only as reference for the monitoring and validation of current satellite cloud products, but also as reference for the design and development of future cloud missions (e.g., assessment of the impact of new channels on the retrieved cloud parameters, impact of new algorithms or algorithm updates, etc.).

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure
AEOLUS	ESA Atmospheric Dynamics Mission – Aeolus
ADNet	Asian Dust Network
ATMO-ACCESS	Project for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities
CALIPSO	Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations
Cal/Val	Calibration and Validation
CDR	Climate Data Record
CLA CA	Clouds & Aerosols Competence Area
CF	Climate and Forecast
CLOUDNET	Cloud Network
CLOUDSAT	Cloud observation Satellite
CLU	Cloud Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS DC
DC	Data Centre
EarthCARE	Earth, Clouds, Aerosols and Radiation Explorer
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMORAL	ESA Mobile Raman Lidar
eVe	European Validation platform for Extensive trials
EPS-SG	EUMETSAT Polar System Second Generation
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurement
FRM4RADAR	Miniature Network for EarthCARE Reference Measurements
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GEO/CEOS	Group on Earth Observations (GEO) to establish the Global Earth Observation System (CEOS) of Systems
GTS	Global Telecommunication System
JMA	Japan Meteorological Agency
L1B	Level 1B (geolocated radiances)
L2	Level 2
LALINET	Latin America Lidar Network
MPLNET	Micro-Pulse Lidar Network
MSG	Meteosat Second Generation
MTG	Meteosat Third Generation
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NRT	Near Real Time
OCA	Optimal Cloud Analysis
RSP	Remote Sensing & Products
SEVIRI	Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager
SI	International System of Units
SWD	Staff Working
TNA	Trans-National Access
UTC	Universal Time Coordinated
VA	Virtual Access

ANNEX 4: Implementation plan for the ESA-EarthCARE pilot project

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Pilot project implementation plan ESA EarthCARE Cal/Val support

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1 Goals

1.1 Current situation

Satellite-based atmospheric Earth observation missions, and in particular EarthCARE of the European Space Agency (ESA), have intense validation needs over a limited lifetime, yet validation resources themselves have a need for long-term continuity. EarthCARE, ESA's and JAXA's Earth Cloud, Aerosol and Radiation Explorer mission, is scheduled to be launched in spring 2024 and addresses the need for a better understanding of the interactions between cloud, radiative and aerosol processes that play a key role in climate regulation and thus is of the general interest of ACTRIS, ATMO ACCESS, and relevant communities.

In order to utilise the global datasets from this mission, the satellite products need to be validated against high accuracy ground-based and airborne measurements. Considering the significance of the EarthCARE mission, and the successive missions to follow (e.g., Aeolus-2 by EUMETSAT/ESA and AOS by NASA), the ATMO ACCESS pilot TNA project aims to set up a tailored framework to meet the needs of the space agencies towards providing quality-assured datasets for Calibration/Validation (Cal/Val) and to monitor the missions during their lifetime utilising the ATMO ACCESS research infrastructures (RI). The validation of such atmospheric missions requires high-quality observations from large networks of appropriate instrumentation such as in ACTRIS.

EarthCARE's active instruments have a narrow swath and sample atmospheric features with small correlation lengths over a broad range of geophysical conditions. Therefore, EarthCARE validation benefits most from a network of RI with a large number and variety of sensors, spread over a large and diverse geographical area, in order to have better sampling statistics (collocation distances and geophysical conditions). Validation of missions such as EarthCARE also requires large communities of experts, as in ATMO ACCESS, who are familiar with correlative instrumentation and with Cal/Val expertise of past relevant satellite missions (such as NASA's CALIPSO and CATS, and ESA's Aeolus).

1.2 Specific objectives

EarthCARE's short commissioning, and its complex, synergistic products, combined with its limited mission life, result in a demanding need for fast delivery of correlative datasets from a ground-based network for validation, which in turn requires thorough preparation, coordination among ACTRIS teams, common tools, harmonised metadata, tailored ACTRIS products, and thorough quality monitoring and intercalibration. Due to the instrumentation onboard EarthCARE, the needs are mainly served by the ACTRIS remote sensing facilities (i.e., aerosol and cloud remote sensing national facilities) and complemented by the airborne in-situ facilities to evaluate higher-level products.

To ensure readiness for the short commissioning phase after launch, a validation rehearsal is needed. With respect to the anticipated launch date of EarthCARE in April 2024, the following specific objectives are foreseen:

- Preparation for the tools and plans for validation

- Development and evolution of validation approaches in collaboration with the international working group for CEOS Cal/Val Best Practices.
- Assessment and removal of biases between EarthCARE and ACTRIS data (e.g., different assumptions, meteorological data (EarthCARE uses ECMWF))
- Preparation activities for data acquisition and rapid processing
 - Fast delivery of ACTRIS products to the EarthCARE (EC) validation team via the ESA Validation Data Center (EVDC). For this, metadata standardisation to GEOMS is needed in order to enable rapid submission of processed collocated data as preliminary data sets which then can be used by ESA, EarthCARE algorithm developers, but also ACTRIS teams to validate EC products.
 - Fulfil special needs of EC validation, e.g. tailoring the data acquisition, quality monitoring and automated processing needs.
- Pre-launch network rehearsal campaign with fast data delivery
 - Cal/Val readiness is key to the success of the mission. Therefore, a rehearsal campaign well before the launch is necessary to ensure readiness of the participants for the validation and/or to identify gaps and shortcomings.
 - The rehearsal campaign will be carried out based on simulated EarthCARE overpasses.
- Post-launch validation with Near Real Time (NRT) data delivery during commissioning phase (directly after launch, planned for spring 2024)
 - Measurements from fixed and mobile facilities during EarthCARE overpasses. Mobile platforms (MP) shall be located close to the orbit ground-track.
 - Fast delivery of preliminary data (NRT data with more rudimentary quality monitoring) to provide quick feedback to EarthCARE team,
 - followed by consolidated data delivery.
 - Feedback for the quality of the L1 and L2 products.
- Intercalibration with
 - other networks (e.g. NASA's MPLNet) to ensure a homogenization of the global validation data set and identifying sources of bias and quality issues.
 - ESA's reference instruments, like the eVe and EMORAL aerosol lidars, to ensure compliance with ACTRIS standards.

2 Implementation

2.1 Tasks

Figure 1 provides an overview of the anticipated tasks within the project which will be explained in more detail in the following:

Project in a nutshell

Fig. 1: Project overview

● WP1: Preparations

Within this work package, the existing ACTRIS infrastructure will be fostered to have readiness for the planned rehearsal campaign (WP2) and further developed where needed. This will include:

- Coordination of the project.
- Setting up specific tools and configurations, e.g., using ECMWF model data for the data analysis to be compliant with EarthCARE's auxiliary data and establishing preliminary quality control measures for the NRT data to be provided to ESA.
- Enabling NRT: This task includes (among others) setting up configuration at the Single Calculus Chain (SCC) for the aerosol lidars, registering, if not yet done, the sun photometer and cloud profiling components to the respective topical centre, and performing the full ACTRIS quality control measures for the profiling National Facilities (NF) as needed for the labelling Step 1b of ACTRIS NF. Furthermore, the NFs need to implement software at their local instrumentation to allow a fast data delivery to the respective data centre (DC) and check the output together with the respective topical centre (TC). In turn, the data centres need to provide the capabilities to host and process the large amount of data in time.
- Training: According to the needs formulated above, training is offered by the TCs and will be provided to NF members.
- Harmonising data formats: This specific work needs to be done at the DCs to ensure that the metadata and data format are compliant with ESA's validation data centre (EVDC).

- **WP2: Network rehearsal campaign**

For the network rehearsal campaign it is aimed to use simulated EarthCARE overpasses for the duration of two months and perform high quality observations with focus on EarthCARE validation needs, in particular:

- Observations at fixed locations: These observations will be performed at fixed locations according to the simulated overpasses. The mobile facilities participate at the location they are currently deployed, mimicking their contribution that is planned for the post-launch Cal/Val campaign.
- Testing workflows (e.g., on NRT submission of measured data, on fast inspection of processed data and on fast delivery of products to EVDC) is one major task within this WP so that the readiness can be evaluated, and/or weaknesses identified and improved until EarthCARE launch. This addresses all involved parties, i.e., the NFs, the TCs and the DCs, in addition to EVDC.

- **WP3: Preparations for the Cal/Val campaign**

In this work package the results of WP2 will be intensively assessed and procedures will be optimised for WP4:

- Setting up optimised configurations: This work package includes an in-depth analysis of the results from WP2 so as to conclude on potential gaps and shortcomings. Based on these lessons learnt, an optimised configuration (both, in terms of hardware and processing chain) will be identified by the NFs together with the respective TC.
- Optimising previous datasets: Based on the optimised configurations, the previous data sets will be re-processed leading to a final rehearsal validation data set, which would allow for an evaluation of the potential of the correlative dataset.

- **WP4: Cal/Val campaign**

During the Cal/Val campaign, the procedure tested and improved in the previous WPs will be applied to generate a significant European contribution to the validation of EarthCARE. Furthermore, experts from ACTRIS will analyse EarthCARE and ACTRIS data and provide feedback to ESA. Detailed tasks are:

- Observations at fixed locations: National Facilities at fixed locations will perform observations according to EarthCARE overpasses and recommend criteria. For example, the current recommendation is everytime when EarthCARE overpasses the station within 100 km radius, correlative measurements shall start at least 1 hour prior overpass and continuing at least 1 hour after the overpass. These recommendations might change depending on challenges encountered during the space mission.
- Mobile observations: Mobile platforms will perform observations as well but will be placed as close as possible to the ground track if feasible. As the exact EarthCARE orbit is just known post-launch, the exact location needs to be defined ad-hoc leading to a dedicated mid-term (e.g. 8 weeks) campaign activity of the mobile facilities. Furthermore, mobile facilities performing air-borne in-situ observations or other added-value measurements will participate and support the validation of the ACTRIS reference observations itself but also EarthCAREs synergistic products (e.g., microphysical aerosols and cloud properties).

- Dataflow: The data delivery to EVDC will be performed as optimised during the previous work packages. This will lead to a fast availability of the data to external (ESA) experts and to the ESA EarthCARE algorithm developers and validation team. In turn, ACTRIS experts who carry out EarthCARE validation studies in this pilot TNA project will receive access to preliminary EarthCARE data as provided by ESA in the frame of EarthCARE Cal/Val.
 - Analysis: ACTRIS experts at NF, TC, and DC level will use EarthCARE and ACTRIS data to perform validation analysis and provide timely feedback to the ESA EarthCARE project in order to improve the products and additional output of the space mission (e.g., NRT data assimilation).
- **WP5: Intercalibration with reference systems**
To ensure a homogenization of the global validation data set including other reference systems and networks for the validation of EarthCARE, the following activities are foreseen in parallel to the previous work packages:
 - MPLNET: At Barcelona NF, an intercomparison to a MPL (Micropulse Lidar) will be performed in cooperation with NASA. MPLs are globally distributed in a dedicated network (MPLNet) and thus are of specific interest for EC validation. The effort will lead to an in-depth characterization of the MPL and thus to a quality indicator of the valuable data set provided by MPLNET for EC validation.
 - EMORAL: The EMORAL (one of the ESA’s reference lidars, operated by University of Warsaw) will be placed at CARS-AHL-INOE for a direct comparison with ALPHA (one of the ACTRIS reference lidars). EMORAL went through an intercomparison in September 2022 and several issues have been found, which were addressed in the meantime. During the direct comparison, QA/QC tests will be applied and optimizations will be made, if possible, in order to qualify the instrument as an ACTRIS compliant system. By doing this, the reference can be transferred to EMORAL.
 - eVe: ESA’s reference lidar eVe hosted by ACTRIS partner NOA will be moved to CARS (Bucharest) and intercompared to become an ACTRIS-compliant reference lidar if quality standards are fulfilled (similar as for EMORAL).

2.2 Timeline

Figure 2 shows the Gantt Chart with respect to the tasks described in Sec. 2.1.

Work packages		2023							2024								
		June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep
		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16
WP 1	Preparation of network rehearsal campaign																
WP 2	Network rehearsal campaign																
Event: EarthCARE workshop Frascati																	
WP 3	Preparation of Cal/Val campaign																
Event: EarthCARE rehearsal																	
Event: EarthCARE launch																	
WP 4	Cal/Val campaign																
WP 5	Intercalibration with reference systems																

Fig. 2: Timeline of planned activities.

The implementation of WP1 to WP4 is planned in chronological order while WP5 will be executed in parallel to WP1-3. The whole activity is aimed to start in June 2023, with the rehearsal campaign (WP2) to be held in September/October the same year. The preparations of the Cal/Val campaign will start after the EarthCARE validation and science workshop in November 2023 and will continue until the foreseen launch of EarthCARE. Finally, the Cal/Val campaign will be performed after EarthCARE launch until September 2024.

An overview of all planned tasks and the estimated costs in terms of SWD is provided in the Table in Sec. 2.5.

2.3 Participants & responsibilities

In the framework of pilot ATMO-ACCESS TNA for EarthCARE Cal/Val, the EarthCARE Project within ESA will provide the relevant support to the ACTRIS team, i.e.:

- Information on the EarthCARE mission as provided to the ESA EarthCARE Validation Team. This includes, e.g., orbit information, updates on products and simulated overpasses.
- Access to preliminary ESA EarthCARE data products and to ESA EarthCARE correlative data repository, following data access protocols defined for the ESA EarthCARE Validation Team.
- Support during the pilot TNA project implementation, e.g., guidance for reporting, interface to the wider Cal/Val participants (e.g. ECMWF, ESA EarthCARE Validation Team, and algorithm developers) and support for data format harmonisation (given by the team at EVDC).

The ESA EarthCARE Project expects ATMO-ACCESS to ensure that the implementation is well coordinated, and that the required resources and services from the ACTRIS teams will be available and be used optimally according to the approved plan.

ACTRIS/ATMO-ACCESS will participate with its selected national facilities, its data centres and sub units, and its topical units as listed in Annex 1. The topical centres are responsible for the quality assurance (including the specific configurations for hardware and data processing) and for the training of the operators. The data centre with its sub units will be responsible for in-time data processing, i.e., providing the capabilities and tools (e.g., data harmonisation) to allow a NRT dataflow from the NF to EVDC.

National facilities (consisting of operational platforms (OP) and mobile platforms (MP)) responsibility is to assure high quality measurements and its rapid delivery to the data centre for the purposes described above. This includes quality control and tests together with the respective topical centres. MPs will, if feasible, be moved to locations which are closer to the direct overpass of EarthCARE. The final decision on location and movement can just be made after EarthCARE launch, when the orbit is known. MP6 (UAV) will furthermore contribute to the validation of microphysical aerosol properties retrieved from, both, EC and ACTRIS aerosol profiling. Some other MPs, like OCEANET for example, will contribute to the validation activity at the site they are deployed during the validation campaign as “chance of opportunity”. Additionally, experts from the ACTRIS NF will analyse EC data together with ACTRIS data for validation of EC and will provide feedback to ESA.

A few non-ACTRIS compliant stations will be included in the activity due to their added value to the project. I.e., these stations can contribute with lidar/cloud profiling instrumentation to the general characterization of the atmospheric state through their dedicated location even though not providing quality controlled ACTRIS variables. Those stations are responsible for a quality-controlled dataflow to EVDC on their own. It is furthermore expected that those stations contribute specifically with their expertise to the validation of EarthCARE, e.g., by representativeness investigations or other topics.

Responsibilities for each provider type are provided in Sec. 2.5 in the form of a summary table.

The working group of this pilot project (i.e., the authors listed on page 1) will coordinate the implementation of this project, monitor the progress and activities during the entire duration, and give feedback. Recommendation for future activities shall be given by ESA EarthCARE Project in terms of the international stakeholders view, all providers and users, and the working group, i.e., all involved parties of this pilot project. The working group will in the end conclude on the project and will formulate final recommendations.

2.4 Resources

The resources needed for this pilot are listed in Annex 1. In principle, all data centre units and topic centres related to remote sensing will be involved as well as the national facilities listed in Annex 1. The resources each component needs are listed in Annex 1 as well. However, please note that **many NFs contribute (partly) on a voluntary basis** within this pilot, i.e., they need a certain amount of SWD (last column of Table in Annex 1) to fulfil the tasks but can support this activity via other funding sources (national, internal, etc.). Thus, only the resources in terms of “Est. access (ATMO)” and “Est. SWD (ATMO)” of the facilities involved are requested within this pilot from ATMO-ACCESS. This means, **out of 3030 SWD in total, 1696 SWD are requested from ATMO ACCESS.**

2.5 Summary table

Objective	Task	Start month	End month	Deliverable(s)	Provider(s)*	Type of access	Estimated no. of access units (SWD)
Preparation of network rehearsal campaign	Implementation of specific Cal/Val QA procedures	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	ATLAS implemented CCRES QA/QC procedures fulfilled	Observational platforms	Remote	63
					Mobile platforms	Remote	27
	Implementation of NRT Cal/Val data submission	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	OBIWAN (or equivalent) implemented CloudNET data stream established	Observational platforms	Remote	61
					Mobile platforms	Remote	27
	Hands-on training on specific Cal/Val procedures	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	Procedures for Cal/Val	TC Units (CCRES-NL, CCRES-FR, CARS-AHL-INOE)	Physical	12
	Remote training on specific Cal/Val procedures	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	Procedures for Cal/Val (follow-up)	TC Units (CCRES-NL, CCRES-FR, CARS-AHL-INOE, CARS-AHL-LMU, CARS-AHL-CNR)	Remote	5
	QA of instruments for the participating platforms (rehearsal campaign)	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	Proposed SCC configurations for rehearsal campaign	TC Units (CCRES-NL, CCRES-FR, CARS-AHL-INOE, CARS-AHL-LMU, CARS-AHL-CNR, CARS-ASP-UVA)	Remote	114
Implementation of the ECMWF model data for the retrievals	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	NRT full processing	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES)	Remote	10	

	Harmonising the data formats	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	EVDC required format	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES, DC-ARES-AERIS)	Remote	15
	Setup of the specific processing configurations at the retrieval units	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	Implemented SCC configurations	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES)	Remote	12
	Setup a centralised QA/QC for the fast data delivery to EVDC	Jun. 2023	Aug. 2023	Implemented data QA/QC	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES)	Remote	10
Network rehearsal campaign	Performance of observations according to simulated overpasses	Sep. 2023	Oct. 2023	8 measurements per month x 2 months	Observational platforms	Remote	272
					Mobile platforms	Remote	48
	NRT submission of measured data	Sep. 2023	Oct. 2023	8 datasets per month x 2 months	Observational platforms	Remote	56
					Mobile platforms	Remote	10
Fast delivery of data products to EVDC (rehearsal campaign)	Sep. 2023	Oct. 2023	8 datasets per month x 2 months	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES, DC-ARES-AERIS)	Virtual	6	
Preparation of Cal/Val campaign	Inspection of processed data and optimization of processing configurations	Nov. 2023	Feb. 2024	Proposed adjustments to SCC configuration	Observational platforms	Remote	140
					Mobile platforms	Remote	30
	Reprocessing of the rehearsal campaign data with optimised configurations	Nov. 2023	Feb. 2024	Optimised rehearsal campaign dataset	DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES)	Virtual	10
	QA of instruments for the participating platforms (Cal/Val campaign)	Nov. 2023	Feb. 2024	Proposed SCC configurations Cal/Val campaign	TC Units (CCRES-NL, CCRES-FR, CARS-AHL-INOE, CARS-AHL-LMU, CARS-AHL-CNR, CARS-ASP-UVA)	Remote	96

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Cal/Val campaign	Performance of observations according to real overpasses (Cal/Val campaign)	Apr. 2024	Sep. 2024	8 measurements per month x 6 months	Observational platforms	Remote	906
					Mobile platforms	Remote	76
	NRT submission of measured data (Cal/Val campaign)	Apr. 2024	Sep. 2024	Measurements in a location (& with a frequency) decided on opportunity	Observational platforms	Remote	204
					Mobile platforms	Remote	37
	Campaign beneath the orbit (mobile observations)	Apr. 2024	Sep. 2024	8 datasets per month x 6 months	Mobile platforms, selected (CARO-Limassol, LIMMACO, LACROS, FComLab)	Remote	364
	Fast delivery of data products to EVDC (Cal/Val campaign)	Apr. 2024	Sep. 2024		DC Units (DC-CLU, DC-ARES, DC-ARES-AERIS)	Virtual	18
Validation of EarthCARE data products against ground-based data (remote access to expertise)	Apr. 2024	Sep. 2024	Report on correlative observations and results	All	Remote	269	
Intercalibration with reference systems	Direct comparison of reference systems with MPL	Jun. 2023	Jan. 2024	Report on direct comparison between ACTRIS lidar and MPL	Observational platform, selected (Barcelona lidar station)	Remote	20
	Direct comparison of reference systems with ESA systems (e.g. eVe, EMORAL)	Jun. 2023	Jan. 2024	Report on direct comparison between ACTRIS lidar and eVe & EMORAL	TC Unit (CARS-AHL-INOE)	Physical	56
	Operation of the ESA reference lidar (EMORAL, eVe) for the direct comparison with the ACTRIS reference lidar	Jun. 2023	Jan. 2024		Observational platforms, selected (PANGEA-EARLINET, Warsaw Observatory Station)	Physical	56
Total estimated access units (SWD)							3030
Total estimated access units supported by ATMO-ACCESS (SWD)							1696

3 Dissemination & exploitation plan

The adaptation/development of the processing chains at the DCs (e.g., including removal of bias between space and ground retrievals) to better meet the requirement for the validation of aerosol and cloud profiling from space and respective results shall be prepared for publication in related journals, and to be included in the CEOS Best practices documentation on aerosol and cloud profiles validation (CEOS document and a special Issue that is under preparation).

The rehearsal dataset as obtained during the rehearsal campaign (WP2) shall be disseminated to EVDC and also to ACTRIS user community for further analysis. The rehearsal activity is planned to be disseminated as an ESA Web article (covering also data centre adaptations and intercalibration plans). Exploitation of the rehearsal datasets and lessons learned will take place by ESA, ACTRIS and ESA EarthCARE Validation Team scientists for their research and validation preparation purposes, and thus will be of benefit for the whole scientific community.

The data from the post-launch validation campaign (WP4) shall be disseminated to EVDC and will be exploited by ESA for data quality improvement of EarthCARE products to the benefit of the user community (scientific and operational users, both including modellers).

Findings from intercalibration activities (WP5) will be exploited in the instruments and processing chains to achieve an understanding of the consistency between the networks and systems involved. This in turn will enable all systems to serve as a consistent reference for intercomparisons with EarthCARE and successive satellites, but also for other global applications. Procedures and analysis shall result in guidelines and reports, also propagated to other networks and individual stations not yet involved.

Dissemination activities include presentations of ACTRIS teams at (post-launch) EarthCARE workshops and international conferences, and publications in journals and ESA reports.

4 Expected impact

The efforts made within this pilot activity will accelerate the currently ongoing implementation of ACTRIS itself and will help to be prepared for future space mission validation and other stakeholder requests. Well validated EarthCARE data is needed to make full use of EarthCARE, this includes scientific activities to better understand the aerosol-cloud-radiation-interaction on Earth as it is of interest of ACTRIS and ATMO-ACCESS in general. Parts of the developments based on ACTRIS and/or well validated EarthCARE data can be directly used for Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), e.g., for being assimilating in the pollution models or even weather prediction models (e.g., cloud properties).

On long term, the developments can be applied on historic data from ACTRIS during period of overlap with CALIPSO and Aeolus to allow bridging between CALIPSO, Aeolus, EarthCARE, AOS (the new NASA mission currently being planned), and Aeolus-2 to the benefit of the essential climate records for atmospheric science.

The tailored products and expertise gained within this project can be used for future space missions among other applications of international stakeholders or science-related institutions. Finally, recommendations of

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the pilot which will be compiled at the end of the project will help for future TNA and/or other activities with space-related agencies and other international stakeholders and will help to understand their needs and the benefits for the ATMO ACCESS community.

Annex 1: List of access providers and effort

Facility	Type of facility	Component(s)	Unit of access (ATMO)	Est. access (ATMO)	Est. SWD (ATMO)	Est. SWD (TOTAL)
CARS-ASP-UVA	TC unit	ARS (photometer)	SWD	40	40	40
CCRES-NL	TC unit	CRS	UWD	26	28	28
CARS-AHL-INOE	TC unit	ARS (lidar)	SWD	102	102	102
CCRES-FR	TC unit	CRS	UWD	44	46	46
CARS-AHL-CNR	TC unit	ARS (lidar)	SWD	42	42	42
CARS-AHL-LMU	TC unit	ARS (lidar)		0	0	60
DC-ARES	DC unit	ARS	SWD	40	40	40
DC-CLU	DC unit	CRS	SWD	38	38	38
DC-ARES-AERIS	DC unit	ARS	SWD	0	0	18
RADO-Cluj	OP	ARS		0	0	54
PAY	OP	ARS+CRS		0	0	26
PANGEA-EARLINET	OP	ARS	UWD	84	84	84
Dushanbe, Tajikistan	OP	ARS	SWD	0	0	41
Leipzig, Germany	OP	ARS	SWD	0	0	41
CVAO, Mindelo, Cabo Verde	OP	ARS	SWD	22	22	54
ATOLL	OP	ARS		0	0	54
Thessaloniki, Greece	OP	ARS		0	0	54
Sofia, Bulgaria	OP	ARS		0	0	54
Pallas	OP	CRS	UWD	27	27	54
Meteorological Observatory Lindenberg	OP	CRS		0	0	54
JOYCE Observatory Jülich	OP	CRS		0	0	54
REXDAN, University Dunarea de Jos of Galati	OP	CRS		0	0	54

Norunda	OP	CRS		0	0	54
Ny-Ålesund	OP	CRS		0	0	54
RADO-Bucharest	OP	ARS+CRS	SWD	86	86	86
AGORA	OP	ARS+CRS	SWD	86	86	86
Cabauw	OP	ARS+CRS	SWD	54	54	54
SIRTA	OP	ARS+CRS	UWD	86	86	86
USRL, Cyprus (FIXED)	OP	NO	DAY	37	37	37
Warsaw Observatory Station	OP	ARS	SWD	144	144	144
Barcelona lidar station	OP	ARS	UWD	74	74	74
OPAR-Moufia	OP	ARS	DAY	54	54	54
EVASO	OP	ARS	UWD	54	54	54
ISAF	OP	NO	SWD	37	37	37
COPDD	OP	ARS	UWD	54	54	54
CIAO	OP	ARS	SWD	54	54	54
CMN-PV	OP	ARS	UWD	54	54	64
Atmospheric Sounding Station El Arenosillo, ARN	OP	NO		25	25	37
SMEAR II, Hyytiälä	OP	CRS	UWD	83	83	83
Chilbolton Observatory	OP	CRS		0	0	39
National Atmospheric Observatory Košetice - NAOK (Atmospheric station Kresin)	OP	ARS	UWD	54	54	54
Observatory Hohenpeissenberg	OP	ARS		0	0	39
Atmospheric RomE joint Supersite	OP	ARS	SWD	0	0	39
OCEANET in Antarctica	MP	ARS+CRS	SWD	0	0	60
CARO-Limassol	MP	ARS+CRS		0	0	134

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LIMMACO	MP	CRS	SWD	0	0	120
KLOCX	MP	CRS		0	0	23
LACROS	MP	ARS+CRS	SWD	67	67	134
FComLab	MP	ARS+CRS	DAY	60	60	120
USRL, Cyprus	MP	UAV	DAY	28	64	64
Total estimated access units (SWD)					1696	3030

Annex 2: List of acronyms

ACTRIS = The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure

AOS = Atmosphere Observing System

ARS = Aerosol Remote Sensing

CAMS = Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service

CEOS = Committee on Earth Observation Satellites

CRS = Cloud Remote Sensing

DC = Data Centre

EC = EarthCARE

ECMWF = European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

ECVT = EarthCARE Validation Team

ESA = European Space Agency

EVDC = ESA Validation Data Center

GEOMS = The Generic Earth Observation Metadata Standard

INCUS = Investigation of Convective Updrafts

JAXA = Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency

MP = Mobile Platform

NASA = National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NRT = Near Real Time (within 72 hours)

OP = Observational Platform

QA/QC = Quality Assurance / Quality Control

RI = Research infrastructures

SCC = Single Calculus Chain

SWD = Staff Working Day

TC = Topical Centre

TNA = Transnational Access

UAV = Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

UWD = User Working Day

